

Details about the Technology Readiness Levels Classification

In this appendix, we present the questions chosen as criteria to classify a tool in a certain TRL that were present in the [TRL calculator](#) created by the Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MCTI) and the sheet in which each Technology Readiness Level was classified.

The questions chosen as criteria were the following:

TRL 1:

- Have basic principles been formulated?
- Has the problem been identified to provide the foundations for the approach?
- Have the antecedents been identified?
- Have the basic assumptions and hypotheses of the technology (project) been determined?
- Have the basic characteristics been defined?

TRL 2:

- Has the experimental design been planned (formulation of research topics and application hypotheses)?
- Has the technology requirements been assessed?
- Has the technology feasibility study (concept and applications) been conducted?
- Have potential users/consumers and applications of the technology been identified?
- Are there examples of applications (restricted to analytical studies with simulated/calculated data)?

TRL 3:

- Does the proof of concept include analytical studies and laboratory experiments?
- Are the performance requirements of the technology established?
- Is there sufficient evidence or detailed analysis of the concept and/or application to support assumptions made/made?
- Has the critical function of the technology been validated through modeling and simulation?
- Have the characteristics of the technology been validated through modeling and simulation?

TRL 4:

- Have tests been performed in a controlled environment (laboratory) for each function and/or separate component?
- Have low-fidelity studies been initiated on the logistics of the technology (interoperability, reliability, ease of maintenance, scalability and safety)?
- Has the functional performance of the element and its components been demonstrated in a laboratory environment?
- Have the results of experiments in a controlled environment (laboratory) shown that the components are operational?
- Has the data obtained been validated to ensure relevance?

TRL 5:

- Has the relevant environment been associated with the component/technology?
- Have scale effects been measured in relation to the model/prototype?
- Have the critical functions and interfaces between the components of the element been identified?
- Are the experiments developed taking into account the real problems?
- Is the model/prototype of the technology ready for testing in a modified condition for the relevant environment with high precision and fidelity?

TRL 6:

- Do prototype/model test results indicate engineering feasibility?
- Has the level of quality, reliability and safety been determined and is it feasible?
- Is there a Final Technical Report?
- Have R&D production results been generated?
- Have production issues been identified?

TRL 7:

- Has each element been tested individually under stress conditions?
- Has performance been demonstrated in an operational environment?
- Has the production planning been validated?
- Has the model/prototype been successfully demonstrated/tested in a real operational environment?
- Have major production issues been resolved?

TRL 8:

- Has the technology documentation been completed?
- Has the technology been qualified through testing and evaluation in a real-world environment/use?
- Is the technology ready for use?
- Is the technology ready for series production?
- Has the technology objective been achieved in a real-world operating environment?

TRL 9:

- Is the technology mature?
- Is the technology operational?
- Technology ready for commercialization?
- Real system fully demonstrated?
- Logistics system implemented?